

Tourists Behavioral Intention to Visit Halal Tourism Destination: An Empirical Study on Muslim Tourists in Malaysia

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Today, the demand for halal tourism has increased dramatically and highlighted as one of the new horizons and fastest-growing sector in the world's tourism industry. **Background Problem:** Malaysia is indeed one of the countries with the most concerned halal segment in the tourism sector. **Research Objective:** The key purpose of this study is to examine the influence of affecting attributes on tourist's behavioral intention to visit Malaysia as a halal tourism destination. **Research Methods:** The development of the research framework is based on the theory of plan behavior (TPB) model. A total of 394 responses were received from the Klang Valley area of Malaysia. For the purpose of analyzing the data, SPSS and AMOS was hired. **Findings:** Findings from the study reveal that, affecting attributes like, "Halal Certification for Food and Beverage", "Destination Image" and "Emotional Incidents" have a significant positive influence on tourist's satisfaction towards behavioral intention to determine the destination. **Research Contribution:** The key significance of this study demonstrated that a large number of Muslim travelers are able to experience Islamic cultures while considering halal tourism products and services in visiting accessible Muslim destinations. **Conclusion:** The conclusions of this research provided insights into the behavioral intentions of Muslim tourists select Malaysia as a destination for tourism.

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INTRODUCTION

Many Muslim tourists visited certain Islamic nations due to the obvious Islamic responsibilities, Halal food accessibility and another such way of life (Battour et al., 2011). These issues have prompts scholars providing guidance on what to meet Islamic criteria including how to facilitate the increasing number of Muslim travellers, conferred by Abdur Razzaque and Nosheen Chaudhry (2013) as well as Lada et al. (2009). Rendering to Wilson and Liu (2011), The behaviour of Muslims is based on Islamic solo instruction. Particularly, Muslim people comply with the teachings of Islam even when they are on holiday (Abu-Alhaija et al., 2013; Delener, 1994; Swimberghe et al., 2011). Many investigations on the Halal tourism show this distinguishing attitude as well as how the Muslim tourists influence in the selection of their tourism destinations (Battour and Ismail, 2016; Isa et al., 2018; Mohsin et al., 2016; Purusottama and Prastowo, 2019; Samori et al., 2016).

The rising number of Muslim travellers worldwide should consider in enormous concentration (Isa et al., 2018). The halal tourism industry 's engagement to the globalized economy is expected to go up 35 per cent to \$300 billion, compared to the US\$ 220 billion by 2019, based on the Global Muslim Travel Index's (Crescentrating, 2019). They also anticipated that the population of Muslim travellers will indeed expand to 230 million, representing many as 10 % of the world 's travellers. In regards, the purchasing power of Muslims will be greater than US\$ 170 billion, according to the Reuters and Standard survey (2019), and in 2021 would be more than US\$ 400 billion. Halal tourism is an increasingly diverse contributor to the global travel industry due to its expansion and scale (Vargas-Sanchez & Moral-Moral, 2020). Interest for halal tourism in Malaysia was enhanced between 2018 and 2019. The report showed that Malaysia has an annual number of roughly 5.15 million tourism arrivals, the overall determinism estimates in 2018 and 2019 were around 5,53 million and 5,38 million Global Muslim Travel Index (2020). This observation suggests that

Malaysia has a strong potential to be a global centre for halal tourism, as Malaysia has many visitors (Harahsheh et Al., 2019).

Religious values play a crucial part in shaping the attitudes and actions of Muslim travellers (Abu-Alhaija et al., 2013; Schänzel & Yeoman, 2015). Previous studies have indicated that the influence of halal certification can be regarded as among the variables that impact tourist behaviour (Blackwell et al., 2001; Mullen et al., 2000). Studies have suggested specific affecting attributes that include individual feelings and emotions which result from using halal food and services, such as "Halal Certification for Food and Beverage", "Destination Image" and "Emotional Incidents" (Isa et al., 2018). The determinant "Emotional Incidents" consequent from the capability of "Halal Certification for Food and Beverage" in enriching the "Destination Image" and turn out to be a renowned destination choice of Muslim tourists (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001; Cengiz & Kirkbir, 2007). The attribute "emotional incidents" measures the utility descended from the spirits or sentimental level, that engendered by a product and it is an essential influence in growing tourist satisfaction. Subsequently, other affecting factors such as relaxation, family togetherness, excitement, fun and safety are significant (Sweeney & Soutar, 2001; Yoon & Uysal, 2005). Therefore, the persistence of this research is to articulate an empirical outline to investigate the relationship of "Affecting Attributes" (Halal Certification for Food and Beverage, Destination Image, Emotional Incidents) and Muslim Tourists Satisfaction towards visiting Behavioural Intention. Affecting attributes has a great influence on satisfaction and their behavioural intentions (Tama & Voon, 2014).

Although Islam requires rigorous commandment on the way of Muslim life in terms of halal selection, the scope to which the following Halal laws are required will probably differ (Razzaque & Chaudhry, 2013; Mukhtar and Mohsin Butt, 2012; Shah et al., 2011). The Islamic tourism

industry is among the world 's speediest emerging forms in the tourism sector, and even with immense potential, it stayed fairly unexplored (Hanafiah & Hamdan, 2020). Very few studies have conducted on the Halal tourism destination choice halal (Hanafiah & Hamdan, 2020), but no studies have found on the influential relationship of affecting attributes on Muslim tourists' satisfaction and behavioural intention to choose Malaysia as a travel destination. It is important to understand, by means of suggestions in the Global Muslim Travel Index survey, if tourists find Halal Certificate for Food and Beverage in selecting tourist destinations, the image of the destination and emotional incidents affect their satisfaction terms (Crescentrating, 2019) Thus, affecting attributes like, "Halal Certification for Food and Beverage (HCFB)", "Destination Image (DI)" and "Emotional Incidents (EI)" acting a crucial part on tourists behavioural intention to select Malaysia as their tourism destination, for example, Isa et al. (2018) stated that, Muslim tourists are conscious that Halal affecting attributes affect their needs and requirements.

As in Halal Tourism, religion has been a major consideration in tourism for a long time. (Wall and Mathieson, 2006; Battour et al., 2011; Henderson, 2011; Jafari & Scott, 2014; Eid & El-Gohari, 2015). Particularly, in relationship to Halal tourism, the three countries that emphasized the attraction of many Arab and Muslim visitors, Malaysia, Lebanon and Turkey, were described by Al-Hamarneh and Steiner (2004). Despite South East Asia becoming the first economic development in the world, Muslim tourists are an important part of halal tourism. Thus, this study aims to examine the determinants affecting attributes to satisfy Muslim tourists to how does it influence their behaviour to select tourism destination. In particular, this research implemented the planned behaviour theory (TPB) and investigated the impact of "Halal Food and Beverage Certification", "Destination Image" and "Emotional Incidents" on the tourist satisfaction with behavioural intent, focused on the revised Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Halal Certification for Food and Beverage on Tourists Satisfaction

"Halal" is governed by the Malay Department of Islamic Development (i.e. JAKIM) in compliance with the Trade Definition Act 2011 with its implementation. The 744 number of Halal certificates given to Malaysia hotels and resorts and the 73 international Halal certificates and authority bodies approved by JAKIM in December was 80 per cent for non-Muslim food and beverage firms 2015 (Islamic Tourism Center, 2015). The Sharia rules are complied with by Muslims in Malaysia. They only consume JAKIM-certified Halal products and services but are also unable to consume pork and alcohol. Muslim people in Malaysia generally apply the same Sharia rules as Muslim travellers from other nations.

A variety of factors have a significant influence on the relationship of halal certification with satisfaction, which is a supporting predictor in the choice of a tourist destination (Rahman et al., 2018). In the case of halal food or halal meal which may be eaten by a Muslim visitor, the phrase implies that there is nothing in food which a Muslim does not consume or which was not slaughtered by Shariah conformity with the principle requirements and in strict compliance with Shariah law (Selim et al., 2019). Halal Sign has been recognised by the entire community as an agent or a linking street since the Mui is given a certificate on the halal labelling so that tourists do not hesitate to purchase it because the institutions that are already holding assured halal labels on goods sold provide customers with specific satisfaction Ahmed (2008). Previous research has demonstrated that user satisfaction effects differ with adjustments in the price of goods. Halal certification foods and drinks are typically price-high because of a stringent regulation's enforcement body (Jalil et al., 2013; Bohari et al., 2013; Ali & Suleiman, 2016; Battour et al., 2018). Thus, the more the quality and price of halal foods and drinks and the more the tourist satisfaction in the purchase of halal foods and drinks will increase (Salleh, 2012). The happiness of Muslim visitors is nothing other than that of

halal-certified food and beverage (Muhamad & Dahari, 2010). However, the significance of the sense of satisfaction of visitors can also be affected by a halal rating, a halal mark, a reputation for shops, advertisement, etcetera (Nooh et al., 2007).

H1. Halal Certification for Food and Beverage has significant influences on tourist's satisfaction.

Halal Certification for Food and Beverage on Tourists behavioural intention

Halal has now become a Global Definition in recent years which not only encompasses slaughter, social justice and welfare procedures but also includes high-quality goods and services to meet customer expectations and needs in the demanding global marketplace Manzouri & Zain (2013). Muslim travellers with different values are willing to seek necessary data regarding halal food guidelines and in halal issues (Hanafiah & Hamdan, 2020). For instance, pious Muslim travellers are still more aware of halal food products than their lesser religious corresponding item and are searching for more updates about halal certification (Wilson & Liu, 2010). Some Muslim travellers have a better sense of the distinction among schools of thought on halal standard concepts, as well as the state's ability to use halal technology, standardisations and other trust factors that are unique within the region (Jeaheng et al., 2020).

In these cases, travellers have faith in the type of certification authority influenced by the accreditation of halal standards (Salleh, 2012). For instance, the size of a Muslim community and its religious ideology may be amongst the most important factors in the country (Battour et al., 2019). Muslim tourists may feel that the reverence of the shariah beliefs is more genuine and stringent in nations to Muslim areas and communities with more Islamic moderate possibilities. Tourists may assume that such countries' halal certificatory are more credible and, thus, their halal certificate can be used to manipulate them than others (Samori et al., 2016). The behaviour of travellers recognizes the impact of a commodity on the logos they know

and particularly those which meet the stated standards (Sirieix et al., 2002). As much visitors admire specific halal attributes, the more relevant they are to buy products with satisfaction (Nguyen et al., 2017). Travellers who agree that the certification of Halal is extremely important and signifies by its purpose to conduct and decide on the purchase of the items. It is thus the conviction of tourists that the halal certification on food and beverage demonstrates the impact of behavioural intent on tourism (Hanafiah & Hamdan, 2020).

H2. Halal Certification for Food and Beverage has significant influences on tourist's behavioural intention.

Destination Image on Tourist Satisfaction

Destination image concept offers an overview in implementing ideas and an assessment process for determining a tourism destination 's image efficiency (Blain, Levy, & Ritchie; 2005). Destination image literature can be divided into four main sources, namely the consequence of the target object, influence on the target image, evaluation of the destination image, and destination image creation. First, the impact of the target picture has been widely studied (Erawan, 2020). The image of the destination was highly and significantly connected to the intention of tourists to visit a location (Chaulagain et al., 2019). Destination image is also identified as, name, sign, emblem, word marking and another image that can identify a destination; the rest promises a visitor satisfaction that can be recognized for the outstanding character of a place that also improves the wonderful memories of a destination (Ritchie & Ritchie; 1998).

In their survey Jeong et al. (2019) have stated that the destination image or brand has a positive relationship to the tourist satisfaction, stressing the significant contributions rendered to personal satisfaction by the destination image and to boost the image of tourists. It is a goal of the authorities regarding the attractiveness of Muslim tourists where destinations can enhance their reputation by using halal-tourism characteristics. Coban (2012) shows that the

image of the destination influences the satisfaction of tourists significantly. The optimistic image of a destination is extremely pleasing, and the negative picture creates unhappiness or discomfort. On this basis, one can assert that Muslim tourism, which positively assesses the image of a travel destination, can visits an attributable halal tourism destination and suggest other tourists as well. Lovelock et al. (2010) clarified that real allegiance is the satisfaction of tourists when very happy visitors or facilities appear to loyal company supporters (tourist destinations).

H3. Destination image has significant influences on tourist's satisfaction.

Destination Image on Tourist Behavioural Intention

The illustration of the destination image involves to the number of individual's thoughts, perceptions, hopes and positive responses for a specific destination (Erawan, 2020). It is regarded being one of the crucial determinants for the efficient growth of tourism sector (Jeong et al., 2019). Therefore, a multitude of studies have concretely explained how the image of the destination is produced and have provided conceptual model to illustrate its specific elements even further (Ratnasari et al., 2020). All such studies usually accept that the image of the destination has a cognitive dimension, i.e. the views or awareness of an individual about either the features or qualities of a specific tourism destination (Coban, 2012), as well as an affective component, i.e. the feelings or emotions that an individual connects to a desired destination (Chew & Jahari, 2014; Papadimitriou, Apostolopoulou, & Kaplanidou, 2015). Researchers have therefore performed experiments to establish a specific scale which can be implemented by applying the theory of plan behaviour to test tourists behavioural intention (Chaulagain et al., 2019).

This paper also suggests that the destination image is connected to the behavioural purpose of tourists to visit the destination of halal tourism. The significant ties between the destination

image and the intention of tourists to visit have also been shown in previous research (Othman et al., 2017; Kitapci et al. 2014; Ha & Jang, 2010). For instance, McDowall and Ma (2010) found that the intention of tourists to visit would be significantly influenced by a higher level of destination image. Previous research that have demonstrated the influence of the destination image on the intention of tourists to visiting consideration (Choi et al., 2018). Lovelock et al. (2010), for instance, indicated that the favourable image of a destination is certain to significantly affect the willingness to consider. Therefore, if tourists have a clear understanding of this, the following hypothesis is given:

H4: Destination image has significant influences on tourists behavioural intention.

Emotional Incidents on Tourists Satisfaction

Around some research, the value of emotions across the tourism sector was acknowledged. For instance, previous research examined post-emotional consumption variables (Muller et al., 1991), the connection among emotions and inclusive satisfaction (e.g., de Rojas & Camarero 2008; del Bosque and San Martin 2008), and emotions as the determinant for entertainment and travelling amenities (Kozak et al., 2004). Another research has explored the influence of emotions on tourist's satisfaction (e.g., Kwortnik & Ross 2007). Kwortnik and Ross (2007) illustrated that visitors experience a variety of beneficial emotions, including relaxation and enjoyment while planning vacations. In their research, Sharma and Nayak (2019) confirmed that the emotional experiences of individual tourists have affected tourist intentions.

Satisfaction stems from the travel interaction that consequently led to the emotional state of the particular vacation spot (Baker & Crompton, 2000; Jayawardena, 2002). Kotler (2019) notes that satisfaction is a person's feelings of pleasure and dissatisfaction that arise from contrasting the output (or outcomes) of a service or product to one's requirements. As such, tourist satisfaction has also been described as a key element in relating tourism market growth and attraction (Salleh, 2012). The Halal tourism

sector has also significantly influenced the preference, availability, delivery of goods and services, and regional halal food for Muslim tourist destinations choice. This optimistic understanding contributes to a positive image and satisfaction in tourists' minds (Kozak & Rimmington, 2000).

H5. Emotional incident has significant influences on tourist's satisfaction.

Emotional Incidents on Tourists Behavioural Intention

The definition of emotional events as a tourist purpose refers to the ability of tourists to consider provided travel options (Othman et al., 2017; Tama & Voon, 2014). In general, the behaviour of Muslim tourist desires is encompassed in the operations of halal tourist facilities, value perception and positive expectations by the service providers (Othman et al., 2017; Kitapci et al. 2014; Ha & Jang, 2010). Analysing emotional tourist reactions and the decision of destination at a certain point provides more knowledge about the forecasting relationships of emotions and tourist behavioural intentions (Stilidis et al. 2017). The emotional incidents are associated in tourism calculation (Sharma & Nayak, 2019). Many other types of research have analysed emotional events on destination choices, for example, travel perceptions have shown, in their selection of tourist destinations according to the Islamic faith, that Muslim tourists can be classed in their nature and magnitude (e.g. Beeho & Prentice 1997). Chhetri, Arrowsmith & Jackson (2004).

The link of emotion concerning the tourist's behavioural intention is verified by several research results (Prayag et al., 2017; Suhartanto & Trijuni, 2016). Studies which focus on Muslim tourist emotions show that the taste experience creates positive perceptions and an increased degree of satisfaction on the behavioural intentions of international Muslim tourists (Ryu & Jang 2006). For example, Prayag et al. (2017) looked from a sign of emotional events with the relationship between tourists' emotional incidents and behavioural intentions.

H6. Emotional incident has significant influences on Tourist's Behavioural Intention.

Tourists Satisfaction on Behavioural Intention

Client expectations for goods and services are the outcome of the customer's satisfaction process with products and services offered by product and services providers (Ratnasari et al., 2020). The consumers' satisfaction with the goods and services they provide will have an influence on the attitudes, depending on how happy the consumer feels (Prayag et al., 2017). The awareness of the actions of tourists would encourage management in efforts to establish Halal goods or services in compliance with Muslim tourist needs and wishes. Tourists also want to behave in terms of the probability of action (Ongsakul et al., 2020). Kitapci et al. (2014) describe behavioural intent as consumer's willingness to comport in some ways to obtain goods or services, to dispose of them and to utilize them. Consumers may, therefore, wish to find knowledge, share their experience with others, buy a specific product or service, or disposal of a certain product. Simamora (2003) notes that behavioural intent is a statement which correlates to further acts. The motive for tourists' behavioural intentions according to Samori et al. (2016) is that the amount or proportion of total interactions by tourists consider to a specific destination. This can be argued based on the above explanation that behavioural intent shows how tourists are inclined to create trust towards the destination in order to achieve their own satisfaction. To tourism authorities, tourist satisfaction is very significant, as it impacts on the number of tourists visits (Ratnasari et al., 2020).

Tourist satisfaction is efficient and has a huge effect on the intention of the visitor's behaviour (Choi et al. ,2018). According to Xiao et al. (2019), satisfaction had a major effect on the behavioural purpose of respondents, which resulted directly in satisfaction as the earlier-received services decided to renew their participation in the further. In their study, Saeed et al. (2020) also mentioned that satisfaction has a significant impact on the intention of tourists.

Desire to visit or recommend to others is theoretically to be pleased with this specific service (Liao et al., 2017). Enjoyment and comfort have a positive impact on the purpose for behaviour; obtaining satisfaction of tourists and positive emotions (such as enjoyment) are important as tourists are more likely to be able to replicate their journey interactions (Foroughi et al., 2019).

H7. Tourists satisfaction significantly influences behavioural intention.

Conceptual Framework

The TPB of Ajzen (1991) represents an extension of the TRA model. The various definitions and problems of tourist activity have been commonly used to define TRA and TPB (Arvola et al., 2008; Baker and White, 2010; Dunn et al., 2011). The TRA primarily claims that the root of actual behaviour is the intention on its own and so its mindset and behavioural control can affect it (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). Ajzen (1991) developed TPB as a further history of actions, including PBC. The TPB is well supported by as many TRAs commonly used research as limited by the

informal presumption of control and not able to adequately predict people's behaviours. TPB was also employed as a way to determine the intention-to-conduct of visitors at that time and extended to a number of fields of research which are defined by attitudes subjective norms and PBC (Armitage & Conner, 2001; Baker & White, 2010; Dunn et al., 2011; Iranmanesh et al., 2019; Soon & Wallace, 2017).

A large number of recent researches are already undertaken to evaluate Halal tourism intent between Muslim tourists (Soon & Wallace, 2017; Afendi et al., 2014; Haque et al., 2015; Rahim & Junos, 2012; Shah et al., 2011). Shah et al. (2011). An investigation has acknowledged TPB and indicated that Halal tourist destination is influenced by mindset, subjective expectations, and perceived behavioural regulation. Thus, this study adopted TPB as a framework to explore the influence on the relationship of affecting attributes, Muslim tourists' satisfaction and tourist's behavioural intention towards destination choice (Figure-1).

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Construct Measurement

The present study structure contains five constraints, specifically; Halal Certification for Food and Beverage (HCFB), Destination Image (DI), Emotional Incidents (EI), Tourists Satisfaction (SAT) and Tourists Behavioural Intention (TBI) where five (5) items of HCFB were adopted from Hanafiah et al. (2020). DI with four

(4) items (Ragb et al., 2020), followed by EI with three (3) items and BI with five items (Akgün et al., 2020). Lastly SAT exhibited by Aliman et al. (2016) with three (3) items.

To conform for the research analysis, elements of every construct are further adjusted slightly. To estimate the level of acceptability among the respondents, the Five-Likert scale was used (e.g. 1= strongly disagree to 5= strongly agree).

Through using English language only, every element in the questionnaire was assembled. "Pre-testing" is often referred to as a pilot test where the purpose of this test is to enhance the consistency of all research tools. It can also work well to calculate the construct (Bryman, 2008). Eventually, twenty-five set of questionnaires (N=25) were disbursed to the tourists who visited Malaysia to collect reviews and opinions on which the rest of the study was carried out, including altering the questions to bring clarification.

Data Collection

Primary data for this study were collected by applying two methods; first, electronic medium (e.g. Google form, WhatsApp and Facebook), the second method was face-to-face distribution through direct interaction. The researcher applied digital or online survey mostly because it is easy to administer, lower cost, faster data collection and analysis, and easy to eliminate missing data in survey responses (Hair et al., 2016). A total of 481 data were collected from Muslim Tourists at the Klang Valley area in Malaysia based on the total population reported at 1,991,068 tourists at the end of December 2019 (mytourismdata.tourism.gov.my). From which 394 data deemed appropriate to perform the analysis. Exact 86 sets of data were discarded after screening and cleaning process are completed. Therefore, based on the suggestion of Glenn (1992), the proposed equation for an infinite population are as follows:

n = (Z^2 * P * (1 - P)) / (e^2) * n
= (1.96^2 * 0.5 * (1 - 0.5)) / (0.05^2) * n
= 384

Note: N= population size, e= margin of error, z= z-score

The equation indicates that, depending on overall population recorded in Malaysia Tourism data, the sample number required for this study was at least 384.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULT

The research used SPSS edition 21.0 and AMOS edition 21.0 software for analysis of the demographic information as well as to test the dimension framework and structural model.

Reliability test

A further reliability test is calculated by using SPSS where Cronbach's alpha shown in Table 1. Using SPSS, the alpha value of 0.952 for Halal Certificate for Food and Beverages (5 items), 0.928 for Destination Image (4 items), 0.905 for Emotional Incidents (3 items), 0.918 for Tourists Satisfaction (3 items) and 0.965 for tourists behavioral intention (5 items) were calculated which indicates that all items in the scale used for measuring the variables involved are reliable. Cronbach's alpha coefficient of a scale should be 0.7 and above as suggested by Pallant (2007).

Table 1: Cronbach's Alpha

Table with 3 columns: Variables, Cronbach's Alpha, N of items. Rows include Halal Certification for Food and Beverages (0.952, 5), Destination Image (0.928, 4), Emotional Incidents (0.905, 3), Tourists Satisfaction (0.918, 3), and Tourists Behavioral Intention (0.965, 5).

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

For analysis and interpretation purposes an exploratory factor analysis was used. Analysis of the factor is done mainly for data reduction.

Kaiser-Meyer - Olkin (KMO) test is typically carried out in study to assess the sample adequacy of the data to be used to evaluate the factor. The purpose of this study is to assess the

degree of unidimensionality of the scales in the collected data. Minimum 20 elements of the five variables were analyzed as factor. To validate the data necessary for factor analysis purposes, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test were conducted, and the findings are presented. The larger value resulting from the KMO and Bartlett's test showed that the data was suitable for factor analysis. Five-factor solutions with a KMO statistic of 0.912 indicate that the sample size was adequate, while another Bartlett's Sphericity test was found to be significant at 0.000. The total variance in the five factors explained was 85.415. The Eigen value is commonly used in deciding on the number of factors and usually a cutoff value of 1 is used to determine factors that are based on eigenvalues. The eigenvalues for the five factors were 8.848, 2.529, 2.216, 2.004 and 1.487 respectively. The results demonstrate that the data were appropriate for factor analysis.

To test the hypotheses, the measurement model was first examined for goodness-of-fit indices and substantial and acceptable factor loadings. The hypothesized measuring model (Figure 2) was evaluated with AMOS. CFA was conducted to test the structure of factor consisting of 20-item scale using AMOS. The correlation of five latent constructs was assumed. According to the modification indices which has provided by AMOS, no indicators were removed from the measurement model as the loadings of each items were 0.7 and above. Hair et al. (2010) denoted any loading value less than 0.5 will be considered to be insignificant. Table 2 demonstrates the overall fit model to ensure a good model fit. The three fit indices (good-of-fit) were assessed. According to Hair et al. (2010), the value of CFI are suggested to be more than 0.90 and RMSEA should be smaller than 0.08 in order to clarify well fit. For χ^2/df , below 3 was considered good value and acceptable. The 20-item scale shows the good model fit and acceptable as the minimum thresholds concerted.

Confirmation Factor Analysis (CFA)

Figure 2: Measurement Model

Table 2: Model Fit

Required value	Obtained value
RMSEA ≤ 0.08	0.040
CFI ≥ 0.90	0.987
Chisq/df ≤ 3	1.403

To assess the measurement model, convergent validity and discriminant validity were conducted. For evaluation of convergent validity, composite reliability was calculated. For the purpose of getting good composite reliability the minimum accepted value was suggested to be 0.7 as recommended by Chin (1988). Additionally, average variance extracted (AVE) value should be at least 0.5 or more is better as recommended by Hair et al. (2006). Current study calculated AVE which shows a good indication. AVE was calculated by using

standardized loadings (Figure 2) of each item by squared of each items of the constructs, then added each items of the construct together and divided it by the number of indicators. The result shows all the AVE values are ranging from 0.763 to 0.854 which was greater than 0.5. The study indicates the value ranging from 0.907 to 0.967 for CR which exceeds the ideal threshold value of 0.7. The test result of the current study can therefore be concluded as the good reliability of all of the items of the constructs.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

Variables	AVE	CR	HCFB	DI	EI	SAT	BI
HCFB	0.800	0.952	0.895				
DI	0.764	0.928	0.401	0.874			
EI	0.763	0.907	0.405	0.355	0.873		
SAT	0.796	0.921	0.384	0.367	0.43	0.892	
BI	0.854	0.967	0.431	0.417	0.38	0.464	0.924

In order to create discriminant validity, it is further needed to show that measures that should not be related are not actually related (Hair et al., 2013). Discriminant validity can indeed be measured by measuring cross loads between buildings using the Fornel-Larcker test and the correlation ratio of Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT). Discriminating construct validity can also be calculated by comparing the square root of the AVE values with the latent variable correlations (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Table 3 shows the high discriminant validity as it demonstrates that the square AVE of each factor exceeds all its correlations with the other factors

Structural Model

The seven (7) hypotheses used in this study are checked to analyze the causal pathways. The results of hypothesis testing are listed according to the hypothesized structural model in Table 4. Among the seven tested hypotheses, all are found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). R^2 value was evaluated. Halal Certification for Food and Beverages, Destination Image and Emotional incidents were accounted for 18.1% of variance

($R^2 = 0.181$) in explaining tourists' satisfaction. Meanwhile, Tourists satisfaction accounted for 25.2% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.252$) in explaining behavioral intention of tourists.

The results of hypotheses signify that H1 which states that Halal certification of foods and beverages will have a positive influence on tourists satisfaction is supported based on $\beta = 0.217$; $SE = 0.045$; $CR = 3.45$. Similarly, H2 was supported based on the β value which shows 0.225, $SE = 0.058$; $CR = 3.71$. For H3 which was hypothesized that significant relationship between destination image and tourists satisfaction exists in between, based on $\beta = 0.208$; $SE = 0.055$; $CR = 3.25$. Similarly H4, H5, H6 and H7 were found to be statistically significant based on the critical ratio ($> \pm 1.96$) which indicates that, destination image has significant influence on behavioral intention of tourists (H4), emotional incidents found to be significant in describing both the tourists satisfaction and behavioral intention thus H5 and H6 were statistically significant. Lastly, H7 was also found to be significant by hypothesized that significant

association of tourists' satisfaction and behavioral intention exists in between.

Table 4: Structural model

H	Relationship	SRW (β)	S.E.	C.R.	p- value	Decision
H1	TSAT←HCFB	0.217	0.045	3.45	***	Supported
H2	TBI←HCFB	0.225	0.058	3.71	***	Supported
H3	TSAT←DI	0.208	0.55	3.25	0.001	Supported
H4	BI←DI	0.213	0.071	3.49	***	Supported
H5	TSAT←EI	0.301	0.061	4.58	***	Supported
H6	TBI←EI	0.125	0.079	1.97	0.048	Supported
H7	BI←TSAT	0.265	0.092	3.92	***	Supported

Note: *p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001

LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER RESEARCH

The research has subsidized to expanding the affecting attributes like “Halal Certification for Food and Beverage”, “Destination Image” and “Emotional Incidents which are inadequate in the literature. Nevertheless, the research had some drawbacks, in which only Muslim tourists visiting in Malaysia participated as respondent. Furthermore, the analysis centered only on Malaysian circumstance, to avoid its widespread use in other countries. This research only explored the limited background of attributes for the choice of a halal tourist destination choice. In future researches, however, more scope should

be included, such as issues of consequences, relaxation, family cohesion, anticipation, fun and protection. The detailed survey is first required to refine the opinion of the participants and define the variables by means of structural equation modelling, which can be tested if they have an effect on the actions of the travellers in a further tour to the desired location.

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

For the advancement of the idea of halal tourism, the research has a specific methodological implicit assumption for the intention of Muslim travellers to choose a holiday destination. The findings of this research indicate that, from a halal viewpoint, halal certification for food and

service, destination image and emotional incidents have important consequences for the satisfaction of tourists, generating behavioural intentions to select destinations. The key findings showed that the number of Muslim visitors finds Muslim friendly affecting attributes to be relative to Islamic cultures influence in their behavioural intention to choose travelling destinations. In the offer of halal certification for food and service, travel companies must become conscious of coordinating tourist objects of destination image and emotional incidents, because of the practice of Islamic laws and restrictions that encourage Muslim visitors to travel halal tourism destinations. Nevertheless, the results indicate that many Muslim tourists are satisfied with halal certificated foodstuff, destination image and emotional incidents which encourage in willing to visiting halal tourism destinations. Therefore, the influence of halal certification for food and service on Muslim visitors behavioural intention should be recognized by tour operators, policymakers or marketing managers, in such a way as to ensure destination image in providing emotional incidents with other facilities to select a destination by the Muslim tourists.

This study clarifies the influence of behavioural intent for the preference of halal tourism destinations and the satisfaction of tourists with affecting attributes. This research offers tourism suppliers, managers and traders an almost summary of the question of Muslim tourists' behavioural intention to provide halal goods and services in the broadest sense to be able to systematically and adjust to their everyday behaviours in the correct circumstances. Hence, "Halal Certification for Food and Beverage", "Destination Image" and "Emotional Incidents" could influence substantially towards the behavioural intention of Muslim tourist to attract Malaysia as a tourism destination.

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